

CST4ALL

Support to the Activities of the Concentrated Solar Thermal Technology Area of the SET Plan

Online R&I Workshop Future Energy Mix with 100% Decarbonization Level

Date and time	24 th March, 2025 10:00am -12:00 pm CET
Venue	Online (via MS Teams)
Free Registration	CST4ALL website or MS Teams website

Electricity market decarbonization using renewable energies is essential to avoiding greenhouse gas emissions. All available renewable sources will be needed, but identifying the optimum electrical mix for each country is challenging and complex due to the many existing boundary conditions, which will differ in each case.

Organised as part of the CST4ALL project, the workshop, which will include keynote presentations followed by roundtable discussions, will assess and discuss the potential and relevant role of CST technologies in contributing to the final objective of full decarbonisation.

Agenda

10:00 OPENING REMARKS

Introduction to CST4ALL project and webinar objectives

Peter HELLER, DLR

The role of solar energy in the SET-Plan

Marina MONTERO, EC DG RTD, European Commission

SSH and gender issues in the CST4ALL project

Yelda ERDEN-TOPAL, METU, Türkiye

10:20 SESSION 1: KEYNOTE SPEAKERS

Concentrating solar power: a solution looking for a problem

Johan LILLIESTAM (Professor of Sustainability Transition Policy, Friedrich Alexander University Erlangen-Nürnberg).

Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement 101075408.

	Optimizing the Electricity Mix with AI: Application to the Spanish Grid Javier BONILLA (Senior researcher of CIEMAT-Plataforma Solar de Almeria).
	Paths to a Climate-Neutral Energy System in Germany Peter NITZ (Head of Dept. High Temperature Solar Thermal and Industrial Processes - Fraunhofer Institute for Solar Energy Systems).
11:00	Live poll on importance of research topics for solar thermal energy systems Collection and prioritization of questions from the audience
11:05	SESSION 2: ROUNDTABLE AND DISCUSSION
	Moderator: Julian BLANCO, CIEMAT-PSA Participants: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cristina TRUEBA. Chair of the IWG-CST of the SET-PLAN. Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities (Spain) - Pedro Horta. Chairperson of University of Evora Renewable Energies Chair. Coordinator of INIESC National Research Infrastructure on Solar Energy Concentration (Portugal) - Alberto CRESPO INIESTA. Director Project Development. ENERGY-NEST (Spain) - Richard Thonig. University of Potsdam (Germany)
11:50	Wrap-up and Conclusions Peter HELLER, DLR
12:00	End of the workshop

CST4ALL team reserves the right to make changes to the workshop program

CST4ALL Coordinator

DLR: Deutsches Zentrum fuer Luft - Und Raumfahrt EV (DE)

CST4ALL Partners

CIEMAT: Centro de Investigaciones Energéticas, Medioambientales y Tecnológicas (ES)

ENEA: Agenzia nazionale per le nuove tecnologie, l'energia e lo sviluppo economico sostenibile (IT)

ESTELA: European Solar Thermal Electricity Association (BE)

GUNAM: Center for Solar Energy Research and Applications (TR)

**Funded by
the European Union**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement 101075408.